

Título del artículo: **A generalization of the notion of hélix**

Autores: **Pascual Lucas y José Antonio Ortega-Yagües**

DOI: **10.55730/1300-0098.3418**

ISSN (revista): **1300-0098**

This document is the Accepted Manuscript version of a Published Work that appeared in final form in Turkish Journal of Mathematics, after peer review and technical editing by the publisher. To access the final edited and published work see <https://doi.org/10.55730/1300-0098.3418>

A generalization of the notion of helix

Pascual LUCAS^{1*}, José-Antonio ORTEGA-YAGÜES²

¹Departamento de Matemáticas, Universidad de Murcia, Campus de Espinardo, 30100 Murcia, Spain,
 ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4354-9736>

²Departamento de Matemáticas, Universidad de Murcia, Campus de Espinardo, 30100 Murcia, Spain,
 ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9521-1051>

Received: .201 • Accepted/Published Online: .201 • Final Version: .201

Abstract: In this paper we generalize the notion of helix in the three-dimensional Euclidean space, which we define as that curve α for which there is an F -constant vector field W along α that forms a constant angle with a fixed direction V (called an axis of the helix). We find the natural equation and the geometric integration of helices α where the F -constant vector field W is orthogonal to its axis.

Key words: helix; osculating helix; normal helix; rectifying helix; Darboux vector; F -constant vector field

1. Introduction

Let $\alpha : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ be a differentiable unit speed curve and let $\mathfrak{X}(\alpha)$ denote the set of differentiable vector fields along the curve. Let $F(s) = \{F_1(s), F_2(s), F_3(s)\}$ be a moving orthonormal frame along α , so we can see F as a differentiable map $F : I \rightarrow SO(3)$. It is easy to show (see e.g. [3, pp. 43–45]) that there exists a unique vector field $D_F(s)$ along α satisfying the equations

$$F'_1 = D_F \times F_1, \quad F'_2 = D_F \times F_2, \quad F'_3 = D_F \times F_3, \quad (1.1)$$

where $()'$ is the usual derivative in \mathbb{R}^3 and \times stands for the cross product. The vector field D_F is called the *Darboux vector associated to the frame F* .

From a physical point of view, along the curve α we have two coordinate systems associated to two references: (a) One associated to the frame F , that may be imagined as being fixed on the curve. This system rotates and is thus accelerating, it is a non-inertial frame. (b) The other is the canonical rectangular coordinates (x_1, x_2, x_3) in \mathbb{R}^3 , associated to the usual canonical basis $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$, that is fixed to the space and is an inertial frame. Obviously, given a vector field W along α , the variation in s of its coordinate functions in the two coordinate systems is not the same. In fact, they are related by the following equation:

$$W' = \frac{d_r}{ds}(W) + D_F \times W,$$

where $\frac{d_r}{ds}(W)$ denotes the rate of change of W as observed in the rotating coordinate system (i.e., in the frame F). The above equation is usually called the *Transport Theorem* in analytical dynamics (see [6, p. 11]). If we

*Correspondence: plucas@um.es

2010 AMS Mathematics Subject Classification: 53A04

1 think of W as a curve in the 3-space, then the above formula tells us that its (absolute) velocity in the inertial
 2 frame $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ is equal to the velocity relative to the moving (rotating) frame $\{F_1, F_2, F_3\}$ plus the velocity
 3 of the rotating coordinate system itself.

4 Motivated by the equations (1.1) and the Transport Theorem, we introduce the following definition.

5 **Definition 1.1** *A vector field W along α is said to be constant with respect to the frame F (or F -constant
 6 vector field) if $\frac{d}{ds}(W) = 0$ (or, equivalently, $W' = D_F \times W$).*

7 The set of F -constant vector fields along α will be denoted by $\mathfrak{X}_F(\alpha)$. In [5], this kind of vector fields are
 8 said to be invariably attached to every point of the curve. If we think of the curve α as the trajectory of a
 9 rigid body, then a F -constant vector can be imagined as a body-fixed vector, [6]. The following result is a
 10 straightforward computation.

11 **Proposition 1.2** *The following properties of F -constant vector fields hold:*

- 12 1) *If W is a F -constant vector field, then W has constant length.*
- 13 2) *If W_1 and W_2 are F -constant vector fields, then $W_1 + W_2$ is a F -constant vector field.*
- 14 3) *Let W be a nowhere zero F -constant vector field and h a differentiable function, then hW is a F -constant
 15 vector field if and only if h is a constant function.*
- 16 4) *W is a F -constant vector field if and only if $W = a_1F_1 + a_2F_2 + a_3F_3$, for certain constants $a_i \in \mathbb{R}$.
 17 Hence, $\mathfrak{X}_F(\alpha)$ is a 3-dimensional real vector space.*

18 A special moving frame is the Frenet frame $F = \{T_\alpha, N_\alpha, B_\alpha\}$, satisfying the well-known Frenet-Serret
 19 equations

$$T'_\alpha(s) = \kappa_\alpha(s) N_\alpha(s), \quad N'_\alpha(s) = -\kappa_\alpha(s) T_\alpha(s) + \tau_\alpha(s) B_\alpha(s), \quad B'_\alpha(s) = -\tau_\alpha(s) N_\alpha(s), \quad (1.2)$$

20 where κ_α and τ_α stand for the curvature and torsion functions, respectively. The vector fields $T_\alpha, N_\alpha, B_\alpha$
 21 are trivial examples of F -constant vector fields. Throughout this paper we will assume that our curves are
 22 non-planar, i.e., with non-zero torsion. For this frame, the Darboux vector is simply denoted by D_α and is
 23 given by $D_\alpha = \tau_\alpha T_\alpha + \kappa_\alpha B_\alpha$. This vector can be interpreted as the angular velocity of the Frenet frame as a
 24 whole. In fact, the rate of change of the frame $\{T_\alpha, N_\alpha, B_\alpha\}$ with s can be characterized as an instantaneous
 25 rotation about the vector D_α , with angular velocity equal to the *total curvature* specified by

$$\omega = |D_\alpha| = \sqrt{\kappa_\alpha^2 + \tau_\alpha^2}.$$

26 Let W be a nonzero differentiable vector field along the curve α . W is said to be a normal vector
 27 field if $W(s)$ belongs to the normal plane for every s ; similarly, we have rectifying or osculating vector fields,
 28 depending on whether $W(s)$ belongs to the rectifying or osculating plane, respectively.

29 The term helix (or general helix, or cylindrical helix, or curve of constant slope) has traditionally been
 30 used to define curves whose tangent vector field T_α forms a constant angle with a fixed direction in the 3-space,
 31 [7, p. 33]. The concept of helix has been extended by considering vector fields other than the tangent vector
 32 field T_α , such as the principal normal vector field N_α (thus giving rise to slant helices, [2, 4]). In this paper,
 33 we propose a new extension of the concept by considering F -constant vector fields.

1 **Definition 1.3** A curve α is said to be a helix if there exists a F -constant vector field W along α that forms
2 a constant angle with a fixed direction V , called an axis of the helix.

3 Without loss of generality, we can assume that W is a unit vector field. In the particular case that W is a
4 normal (osculating or rectifying, resp.) vector field then α is called a normal (osculating or rectifying, resp.)
5 helix. Note that we recover the notion of cylindrical helix or slant helix when the F -constant vector field W
6 is given by T_α or N_α , respectively. Note also that the term osculating helix has been previously used to refer
7 to the circular helix passing through a point of a curve, having the same tangent, curvature vector and torsion,
8 [7, p. 42].

9 In this paper, we solve the following problem:

10 *How are characterized the helices α when the F -constant vector field W is orthogonal to its axis*
11 *V ?*

12 Note that when the vector field W is T_α , N_α or B_α , then the curve α is nothing but a plane curve or a
13 cylindrical helix. Therefore, in the following sections we will address the question when the vector field W is
14 expressed as a linear combination of at least two vector fields of the Frenet frame.

15 2. Normal helices

16 2.1. Natural equation of normal helices

17 Let α be a nonplanar curve in \mathbb{R}^3 with Frenet apparatus $\{\kappa_\alpha, \tau_\alpha; T_\alpha, N_\alpha, B_\alpha\}$, and assume that α is a normal
18 helix with axis V , V being a constant vector. Suppose that there is a nonzero constant angle $\theta \in (-\pi/2, \pi/2)$
19 such that $W = \cos \theta N_\alpha + \sin \theta B_\alpha$ is orthogonal to V . Hence we can write

$$V = \lambda T_\alpha + \mu(\sin \theta N_\alpha - \cos \theta B_\alpha), \quad (2.1)$$

for certain differentiable functions λ and μ . By taking derivative in (2.1) we get

$$\lambda' - \mu \sin \theta \kappa_\alpha = 0, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\sin \theta \mu' + \lambda \kappa_\alpha + \mu \cos \theta \tau_\alpha = 0, \quad (2.3)$$

$$-\cos \theta \mu' + \mu \sin \theta \tau_\alpha = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

20 From equation (2.4) we have

$$\mu = e^{\tan \theta \int \tau_\alpha}, \quad (2.5)$$

21 that jointly with (2.3) leads to

$$\lambda = -\sec \theta \rho e^{\tan \theta \int \tau_\alpha}, \quad (2.6)$$

22 where $\rho = \tau_\alpha / \kappa_\alpha$ is called the Lancret curvature. Finally, putting equations (2.5) and (2.6) in (2.2) yields

$$-\sec \theta (\rho' + \tan \theta \tau_\alpha \rho) = \sin \theta \kappa_\alpha, \quad (2.7)$$

23 and then

$$-\rho' = \sin \theta \cos \theta \kappa_\alpha + \tan \theta \tau_\alpha \rho. \quad (2.8)$$

24 Therefore

$$\frac{\kappa_\alpha}{\cos^2 \theta \kappa_\alpha^2 + \tau_\alpha^2} \left(\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha} \right)' = -\tan \theta. \quad (2.9)$$

1 Conversely, let α be a curve in \mathbb{R}^3 satisfying equation (2.9), for a nonzero constant $\theta \in (-\pi/2, \pi/2)$. Let V
 2 be the vector field given in (2.1), where μ and λ are defined by equations (2.5) and (2.6), respectively. Then
 3 equations (2.3) and (2.4) are satisfied. On the other hand, from equation (2.9) we easily get (2.7), and then we
 4 deduce (2.2) since

$$\mu \sin \theta \kappa_\alpha = -\sec \theta (\rho' \mu + \tan \theta \tau_\alpha \rho \mu) = \lambda'.$$

5 Hence, there is a constant θ such that the vector field $\cos \theta N_\alpha + \sin \theta B_\alpha$ is orthogonal to a constant direction
 6 V , so α is a normal helix.

7 Summing up, we have shown the following result (we also include the case $\theta = 0$).

8 **Theorem 2.1** *Let α be a nonplanar arclength parametrized curve in \mathbb{R}^3 , with curvature $\kappa_\alpha > 0$ and torsion*
 9 *τ_α . Then α is a normal helix (with W orthogonal to V) if and only if the following equation holds*

$$\frac{\kappa_\alpha}{\cos^2 \theta \kappa_\alpha^2 + \tau_\alpha^2} \left(\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha} \right)' = -\tan \theta,$$

10 for a certain constant $\theta \in (-\pi/2, \pi/2)$.

11 2.2. Geometric interpretation of normal helices

12 Let α be a normal helix with axis V , and assume that V is orthogonal to the F -constant vector field $W =$
 13 $\cos \theta N_\alpha + \sin \theta B_\alpha$, θ being a constant. Let us consider $C_{\alpha,V}$ the cylinder parametrized by $X(t, z) = \alpha(t) + zV$,
 14 then we have $N = X_t \times X_z = T_\alpha \times V = \cos \theta N_\alpha + \sin \theta B_\alpha$, up to a sign. This shows that the principal normal
 15 vector field N_α of the curve α makes a constant angle θ with the unit vector field N normal to the cylinder
 16 $C_{\alpha,V}$. It is not difficult to see that this condition characterizes the normal helices.

Let $M = C_{\beta,V}$ be a general cylinder parametrized by $X(t, z) = \beta(t) + zV$, where β is a unit planar
 curve and V is a unit vector orthogonal to that plane. If $\{T_\beta, N_\beta\}$ is the Frenet frame of β , assume that
 the unit normal vector to the cylinder is given by $N(t, z) = T_\beta(t) \times V = N_\beta(t)$. Let us assume that
 $\alpha(s) = X(t(s), z(s))$, $s \in I$, is an arclength parametrized curve in M such that N_α makes a constant angle θ
 with N . A straightforward computation yields

$$T_\alpha(s) = \cos \varphi(s) T_\beta(t(s)) + \sin \varphi(s) V, \tag{a}$$

$$N_\alpha(s) = \sin \theta (-\sin \varphi(s) T_\beta(t(s)) + \cos \varphi(s) V) + \cos \theta N, \tag{b} \tag{2.10}$$

$$B_\alpha(s) = -\cos \theta (-\sin \varphi(s) T_\beta(t(s)) + \cos \varphi(s) V) + \sin \theta N, \tag{c}$$

17 where $\varphi \in C^\infty(I)$ is a differentiable function with $t'(s) = \cos \varphi(s)$ and $z'(s) = \sin \varphi(s)$. It is easy to see that

$$V = \sin \varphi(s) T_\alpha(s) + \cos \varphi(s) (\sin \theta N_\alpha(s) - \cos \theta B_\alpha(s)), \tag{2.11}$$

18 and then we can define the F -constant vector field $W = \cos \theta N_\alpha + \sin \theta B_\alpha$ satisfying $\langle W, V \rangle = 0$, showing
 19 that α is a normal helix. Therefore, we have proved the following result.

20 **Theorem 2.2** *A curve α in \mathbb{R}^3 is a normal helix with axis V if and only if α lies on a cylinder C and its*
 21 *principal normal vector field makes a constant angle with the normal vector field to the cylinder.*

1 Note that when $\theta = 0$ then α is a geodesic of the cylinder, and so it is a cylindrical helix. Hence,
 2 Theorem 2.2 is an extension of the well known theorem of Lancret that characterizes the cylindrical helices as
 3 the geodesics of the cylinders.

We finish this section with the following result about curves $\alpha(s)$ in a cylinder $C_{\beta,V}$. By taking derivative in equations (a) and (c) of (2.10) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_\alpha(s)N_\alpha(s) &= \varphi'(s)(-\sin \varphi(s)T_\beta(t(s)) + \cos \varphi(s)V) + \cos^2 \varphi(s)\kappa_\beta(t(s))N_\beta(t(s)), \\ -\tau_\alpha(s)N_\alpha(s) &= \varphi'(s)\cos \theta(\cos \varphi(s)T_\beta(t(s)) + \sin \varphi(s)V) + \\ &\quad + \cos \varphi(s)\kappa_\beta(-\sin \theta T_\beta(t(s)) + \cos \theta \sin \varphi N_\beta(t(s))). \end{aligned}$$

4 These two equations lead to the following result.

Proposition 2.3 *Let $\alpha(s) = X(t(s), z(s))$ be an arclength parametrized curve in a cylinder $C_{\beta,V}$. The principal normal vector field N_α makes a constant angle θ with the normal to the cylinder if and only if there is a differentiable function φ such that the following equations hold*

$$t'(s) = \cos \varphi(s), \tag{2.12}$$

$$z'(s) = \sin \varphi(s), \tag{2.13}$$

$$\varphi'(s) = \tan \theta \cos^2(\varphi(s)) \kappa_\beta(t(s)). \tag{2.14}$$

5 Moreover, the curvature and torsion of α are given by

$$\kappa_\alpha(s) = \frac{\cos^2 \varphi(s)}{\cos \theta} \kappa_\beta(t(s)), \quad \tau_\alpha(s) = -\sin \varphi(s) \cos \varphi(s) \kappa_\beta(t(s)). \tag{2.15}$$

On the other hand, from (2.15) we get

$$\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha}(s) = -\cos \theta \tan \varphi(s),$$

6 and since $(\tan \varphi)'(s) = \tan \theta \kappa_\beta(t(s))$, we have that only in circular cylinders there exist normal helices that
 7 are also rectifying curves, see [1].

8 2.3. An example: normal helices in circular cylinders

Let $C_{\beta,V}$ be a cylinder over a circle β of radius one. Then from Proposition 2.3 we get

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(s) &= \arctan(\tan(\theta)s), \\ t(s) &= \cot(\theta) \sinh^{-1}(\tan(\theta)s) + t_0, \\ z(s) &= \cot(\theta) \sqrt{1 + \tan^2(\theta)s^2} + z_0, \end{aligned}$$

where θ, t_0, z_0 are constants. Hence, a family of normal helices in the cylinder is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(s) &= \left(\cos(\cot(\theta) \sinh^{-1}(\tan(\theta)s) + t_0), \right. \\ &\quad \left. \sin(\cot(\theta) \sinh^{-1}(\tan(\theta)s) + t_0), \right. \\ &\quad \left. \cot(\theta) \sqrt{1 + \tan^2(\theta)s^2} + z_0 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1. A normal helix with $\theta = \pi/36$ in a circular cylinder

- 1 Moreover, from (2.15) we obtain that the curvature and torsion of α are given by

$$\kappa_\alpha(s) = \frac{\cos \theta}{\cos^2 \theta + \sin^2(\theta) s^2}, \quad \tau_\alpha(s) = \frac{-\sin \theta \cos(\theta) s}{\cos^2 \theta + \sin^2(\theta) s^2}. \quad (2.16)$$

- 2 Note that these curves verify that $\tau_\alpha/\kappa_\alpha(s) = -\sin(\theta)s$, so they are rectifying curves.

We can reparametrize the curves α to obtain a simpler expression. Indeed, let us consider the change of parameter $\tan(\theta)s = \sinh(\tan(\theta)t)$, then

$$\alpha(t) = (\cos(t + t_0), \sin(t + t_0), \cot(\theta) \cosh(\tan(\theta)t) + z_0),$$

- 3 and the curvature and torsion can be computed as follows

$$\kappa_\alpha(t) = \frac{\sec \theta}{\cosh^2(\tan(\theta)t)}, \quad \tau_\alpha(t) = \frac{-\sinh(\tan(\theta)t)}{\cosh^2(\tan(\theta)t)}. \quad (2.17)$$

- 4 A picture of a normal helix is shown in figure 1.

5 3. Osculating helices

6 3.1. Natural equation of osculating helices

- 7 Let α be a nonplanar osculating helix with axis V . Then there is an osculating vector field $W = \cos \theta T_\alpha +$
 8 $\sin \theta N_\alpha$, for a nonzero constant angle $\theta \in (-\pi/2, \pi/2)$, which is orthogonal to V . Hence we can write

$$V = \mu(-\sin \theta T_\alpha + \cos \theta N_\alpha) + \lambda B_\alpha, \quad (3.1)$$

for certain differentiable functions λ and μ . By derivating here we obtain the following equations

$$-\sin \theta \mu' - \mu \cos \theta \kappa_\alpha = 0, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\cos \theta \mu' - \lambda \tau_\alpha - \mu \sin \theta \kappa_\alpha = 0, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\lambda' + \mu \cos \theta \tau_\alpha = 0. \quad (3.4)$$

- 9 From equation (3.2) we get

$$\mu = e^{-\cot \theta \int \kappa_\alpha}, \quad (3.5)$$

1 that jointly with (3.3) yields

$$\lambda = \frac{-1}{\sin \theta \rho} e^{-\cot \theta \int \kappa_\alpha}, \quad (3.6)$$

2 where ρ is the Lancret curvature. On the other hand, by putting equations (3.5) and (3.6) in (3.4), we get

$$\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \left(\frac{\rho'}{\rho^2} + \cot \theta \kappa_\alpha \frac{\rho}{\rho^2} \right) = -\cos \theta \tau_\alpha,$$

3 and then

$$-\rho' = \sin \theta \cos \theta \tau_\alpha \rho^2 + \cot \theta \kappa_\alpha \rho,$$

4 which can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\kappa_\alpha^2}{\kappa_\alpha^2 + \sin^2 \theta \tau_\alpha^2} \left(\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha} \right)' = -\cot \theta \tau_\alpha. \quad (3.7)$$

5 Note that this equation is equivalent to

$$\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha^2 + \sin^2 \theta \tau_\alpha^2} \left(\frac{\kappa_\alpha}{\tau_\alpha} \right)' = \cot \theta. \quad (3.8)$$

6 Now, we will see that this equation characterizes the osculating helices. Indeed, let α be a curve in \mathbb{R}^3 satisfying
 7 (3.8) for a nonzero constant $\theta \in (-\pi/2, \pi/2)$. Let us define a vector field V as in (3.1), where λ and μ are given
 8 by (3.6) and (3.5), respectively. Then equations (3.2) and (3.3) are satisfied. Finally, it is straightforward to see
 9 that equation (3.8) leads to (3.4). Then there exists a constant θ such that $\cos \theta T_\alpha + \sin \theta N_\alpha$ is orthogonal to
 10 the constant direction V , that is, α is an osculating helix.

11 We have proved the following characterization of the osculating helices (we also include the cases $\theta =$
 12 $\pm\pi/2$).

Theorem 3.1 *Let α be a nonplanar arclength parametrized curve in \mathbb{R}^3 , with curvature $\kappa_\alpha > 0$ and torsion τ_α . Then α is an osculating helix (with W orthogonal to V) if and only if the following equation holds*

$$\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha^2 + \sin^2 \theta \tau_\alpha^2} \left(\frac{\kappa_\alpha}{\tau_\alpha} \right)' = \cot \theta,$$

13 for a nonzero constant angle $\theta \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$.

14 3.2. Normal helices and osculating helices

15 Let $\alpha(s)$ be a normal helix with Frenet apparatus $\{\kappa_\alpha, \tau_\alpha; T_\alpha, N_\alpha, B_\alpha\}$. Then the curve

$$\bar{\alpha}(s) = \int_{s_0}^s B_\alpha(t) dt \quad (3.9)$$

16 is an arclength parametrized curve, and without loss of generality its Frenet frame is given by

$$T_{\bar{\alpha}} = B_\alpha, \quad N_{\bar{\alpha}} = -N_\alpha, \quad B_{\bar{\alpha}} = T_\alpha.$$

1 Hence their curvature and torsion are given by $\kappa_{\bar{\alpha}} = \tau_{\alpha}$ and $\tau_{\bar{\alpha}} = \kappa_{\alpha}$. It is straightforward to see that $\bar{\alpha}$
 2 satisfies (3.8), and so it is an osculating helix.

3 On the other hand, and following a similar reasoning, it can be proved that if $\bar{\alpha}$ is an osculating helix
 4 then the curve

$$\alpha(s) = \int_{s_0}^s B_{\bar{\alpha}}(t) dt \quad (3.10)$$

5 is a normal helix. Therefore, and in a certain sense, normal helices and osculating helices can be considered as
 6 duals of each other.

7 4. Rectifying helices

Let α be a nonplanar curve in \mathbb{R}^3 with Frenet apparatus $\{\kappa_{\alpha}, \tau_{\alpha}; T_{\alpha}, N_{\alpha}, B_{\alpha}\}$, and assume that α is a
 rectifying helix with axis V , V being a constant vector. Let us suppose there is a constant angle θ such that
 the rectifying vector field $W = \cos \theta B_{\alpha} + \sin \theta T_{\alpha}$ is orthogonal to V . Hence we can write

$$V = \lambda N_{\alpha} + \mu(\sin \theta B_{\alpha} - \cos \theta T_{\alpha}),$$

for certain differentiable functions λ and μ . By taking derivative there we get

$$-\lambda \kappa_{\alpha} - \mu' \cos \theta = 0,$$

$$\lambda' - \mu \cos \theta \kappa_{\alpha} - \mu \sin \theta \tau_{\alpha} = 0,$$

$$\lambda \tau_{\alpha} + \mu' \sin \theta = 0.$$

8 From these equations we easily deduce that $\tau_{\alpha}/\kappa_{\alpha}$ is constant, and so α is a cylindrical helix. Since every
 9 cylindrical helix is also a rectifying helix, then we have proved the following result.

10 **Theorem 4.1** *Let α be an arclength parametrized curve in \mathbb{R}^3 with curvature $\kappa_{\alpha} > 0$. Then α is a rectifying*
 11 *helix (with W orthogonal to V) if and only if it is a cylindrical helix.*

12 5. The general case

13 Let us assume, in this section, that the unit F -constant vector field W along α is given by $W = aT_{\alpha} + bN_{\alpha} + cB_{\alpha}$,
 14 where a, b, c are nonzero constants with $a^2 + b^2 + c^2 = 1$ (the other cases have already been analyzed in the
 15 preceding sections). Since we are assuming that $\langle W, V \rangle = 0$, then there exists two differentiable functions λ, μ
 16 such that

$$V = \lambda(-cT_{\alpha} + aB_{\alpha}) + \mu(-cN_{\alpha} + bB_{\alpha}), \quad (5.1)$$

and by derivating here we obtain the following equations:

$$0 = \lambda' - \mu \kappa_{\alpha}, \quad (5.2)$$

$$0 = c\mu' + \lambda(c\kappa_{\alpha} + a\tau_{\alpha}) + b\mu\tau_{\alpha}, \quad (5.3)$$

$$0 = a\lambda' + b\mu' - c\mu\tau_{\alpha}. \quad (5.4)$$

17 From (5.2) and (5.4) we get

$$\mu' = \frac{1}{b}(c\tau_{\alpha} - a\kappa_{\alpha})\mu, \quad (5.5)$$

1 that jointly with (5.3) leads to

$$c\mu(c\tau_\alpha - a\kappa_\alpha) + \lambda b(c\kappa_\alpha + a\tau_\alpha) + b^2\mu\tau_\alpha = 0.$$

2 Then

$$\lambda = g\mu, \quad \text{with } g = \frac{ac\kappa_\alpha - (b^2 + c^2)\tau_\alpha}{b(c\kappa_\alpha + a\tau_\alpha)}. \quad (5.6)$$

3 Now, by using (5.2) and (5.5) we obtain

$$b\kappa_\alpha = bg' + g(c\tau_\alpha - a\kappa_\alpha). \quad (5.7)$$

4 Since g' is given by

$$g' = \frac{-c\kappa_\alpha^2}{b(c\kappa_\alpha + a\tau_\alpha)^2} \left(\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha} \right)',$$

5 a straightforward computation from (5.7) yields

$$\frac{\kappa_\alpha^2}{c\kappa_\alpha((1-c^2)\kappa_\alpha^2 + (1-3a^2)\tau_\alpha^2) + a\tau_\alpha((1-a^2)\tau_\alpha^2 + (1-3c^2)\kappa_\alpha^2)} \left(\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha} \right)' = -\frac{1}{b}. \quad (5.8)$$

6 Conversely, let α be a curve satisfying (5.8) for certain nonzero constants a, b, c . Let V be the nonzero vector
 7 field given in (5.1), where μ and λ are given by (5.5) and (5.6), respectively. As in the preceding sections, it is a
 8 straightforward (if somewhat laborious) calculation to check that equations (5.2)–(5.4) are satisfied. Therefore,
 9 we have found a F -constant vector field $W = aT_\alpha + bN_\alpha + cB_\alpha$ which is orthogonal to the fixed direction V .

10 To finish this section, and in order to consider also the cases in which any of the constants a, b or c
 11 could be zero, let us note that equation (5.8) can be rewritten as

$$-b\kappa_\alpha^2 \left(\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha} \right)' = c\kappa_\alpha((1-c^2)\kappa_\alpha^2 + (1-3a^2)\tau_\alpha^2) + a\tau_\alpha((1-a^2)\tau_\alpha^2 + (1-3c^2)\kappa_\alpha^2), \quad (5.9)$$

12 and then we have all the cases previously analyzed:

W	α is a	Eq. (5.9) reduces to
T_α	plane curve	$\rho = 0$
N_α	cylindrical helix	$\rho' = 0$
B_α	plane curve	$\rho = 0$
$bN_\alpha + cB_\alpha$	normal helix	Eq. (2.9)
$aT_\alpha + bN_\alpha$	osculating helix	Eq. (3.8)
$aT_\alpha + cB_\alpha$	rectifying helix	$\rho' = 0$
$aT_\alpha + bN_\alpha + cB_\alpha$	helix	Eq. (5.8)

14 In conclusion, we have shown the following result.

15 **Theorem 5.1** *Let α be a nonplanar arclength parametrized curve in \mathbb{R}^3 with curvature $\kappa_\alpha > 0$ and torsion*
 16 *τ_α . Then α is a helix (associated to the unit F -constant vector field $W = aT_\alpha + bN_\alpha + cB_\alpha$ orthogonal to the*

1 axis) if and only if the following equation holds

$$-b\kappa_\alpha^2 \left(\frac{\tau_\alpha}{\kappa_\alpha} \right)' = c\kappa_\alpha((1-c^2)\kappa_\alpha^2 + (1-3a^2)\tau_\alpha^2) + a\tau_\alpha((1-a^2)\tau_\alpha^2 + (1-3c^2)\kappa_\alpha^2),$$

2 with $a^2 + b^2 + c^2 = 1$.

3 We finish this section with the geometric interpretation of helices in the general case.

4 **Theorem 5.2** Let α be a nonplanar arclength parametrized curve in \mathbb{R}^3 with curvature $\kappa_\alpha > 0$ and torsion
5 τ_α . Then α is a helix (associated to the unit F -constant vector field $W = aT_\alpha + bN_\alpha + cB_\alpha$ orthogonal to the
6 axis V) if and only if α is contained in a cylinder $C_{\beta,V}$ and satisfies the following equation

$$a \tan \varphi + b \sin \theta - c \cos \theta = 0, \quad (5.10)$$

7 where a, b, c are real constants and the angles φ and θ are given by

$$\sin \varphi = \langle T_\alpha, V \rangle, \quad \sin \theta \langle B_\alpha, V \rangle + \cos \theta \langle N_\alpha, V \rangle = 0.$$

8 **Proof** We will follow the same reasoning as for proving Theorem 2.2. Let us first prove the reciprocal part.
9 Let $X(t, z) = \beta(t) + zV$ be the canonical parametrization of $C_{\beta,V}$ and suppose $\alpha(s) = X(t(s), z(s))$. Although
10 equations (2.10) and (2.11) have been obtained for the case where θ is constant, they also remain valid in the
11 non-constant case, and so the F -constant vector field $W = aT_\alpha + bN_\alpha + cB_\alpha$ satisfies $\langle V, W \rangle = 0$. Hence α is
12 a helix with axis V and F -constant vector field W orthogonal to it.

13 Now, let us consider α a helix with axis V , and suppose there is a F -constant vector field $W =$
14 $aT_\alpha + bN_\alpha + cB_\alpha$ satisfying $\langle V, W \rangle = 0$. Then α is contained in the cylinder $C_{\alpha,V}$, which can be locally
15 parametrized by $X(t, z) = \beta(t) + zV$, where $\beta(t)$ is a plane curve in $C_{\alpha,V}$ orthogonal to V . Then equations
16 (2.10) and (2.11) are satisfied, and the condition $\langle V, W \rangle = 0$ implies equation (5.10), since $\cos \varphi \neq 0$ (otherwise,
17 α would be a plane curve). \square

18 Following a reasoning similar to the one used to prove Proposition 2.3, we can obtain from Theorem 5.2
19 the following result (which generalizes Proposition 2.3 to the case where θ is not constant). We leave the proof
20 to the reader.

Proposition 5.3 Let $\alpha(s) = X(t(s), z(s))$ be an arclength parametrized curve in a cylinder $C_{\beta,V}$. Then α
satisfies equation (5.10), for a non constant function $\theta \equiv \theta(s)$, if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} t'(s) &= \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + (-b \sin \theta + c \cos \theta)^2}}, \\ z'(s) &= \frac{-b \sin \theta + c \cos \theta}{\sqrt{a^2 + (-b \sin \theta + c \cos \theta)^2}}, \\ \kappa_\beta(t(s)) &= -\frac{(b \cos \theta + c \sin \theta)\theta'}{a \tan \theta}. \end{aligned}$$

21 Acknowledgement

22 This research is part of the grant PID2021-124157NB-I00, funded by MCIN/ AEI/ 10.13039/ 501100011033/
23 “ERDF A way of making Europe”. Also supported by “Ayudas a proyectos para el desarrollo de investigación

1 científica y técnica por grupos competitivos”, included in the “Programa Regional de Fomento de la Investigación
2 Científica y Técnica (Plan de Actuación 2022)” of the Fundación Séneca-Agencia de Ciencia y Tecnología de la
3 Región de Murcia, Ref. 21899/PI/22.

4 **References**

- 5 [1] Chen BY. When does the position vector of a space curve always lie in its rectifying plane? *American Mathematical*
6 *Monthly* 2003; 110: 147–152. doi: 10.2307/3647775
- 7 [2] Izumiya S, Takeuchi N. New special curves and developable surfaces. *Turkish Journal of Mathematics* 2004; 28:
8 153–163. <https://journals.tubitak.gov.tr/math/vol28/iss2/6/>
- 9 [3] Kreyszig E. *Differential Geometry*. Toronto, Canada: University of Toronto Press, 1959.
- 10 [4] Lucas P, Ortega-Yagües JA. Slant helices in the Euclidean 3-space revisited. *Bulletin of the Belgian Mathematical*
11 *Society - Simon Stevin* 2016; 23: 133–150. doi: 10.36045/bbms/1457560859
- 12 [5] Santaló L. On the converse of a theorem of Jacobi relative to space curves. *Universidad Nacional de Tucumán,*
13 *Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Tecnología, Revista Serie A, Matemática y Física Teórica* 1967; 17: 83–89 (in
14 Spanish).
- 15 [6] Schaub H, Junkins JL. *Analytical Mechanics of Space Systems*, 2ed. Virginia, USA: American Institute of Aero-
16 nautics & Astronautics, 2009.
- 17 [7] Struik DJ. *Lectures on Classical Differential Geometry*, 2ed. New York, USA: Dover Publ., Inc., 1961.